

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

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Abbreviations list

API	Application Programming Interface
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
CC0	Creative Commons
D[X]	Deliverable [X]
DCS	DMP Common Standard
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPOs	Data Protection Officers
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FP	Framework Programme
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
ID	Identifier or Identification
IT	Information Technology
maDMPs	machine-actionable Data Management Plans
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PTA	Plan-Track-Assess
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph

TIER2 Enhancing Trust, Integrity and Efficiency in Research through next-level
Reproducibility

URL Uniform Resource Locator

Executive Summary

This first version of the D4.2 Horizon Europe Report lays the foundation for validating how OpenAIRE services, namely **ARGOS, the OpenAIRE Graph, and the Metadata Validator**, can be combined to support **a structured, semi-automated approach to planning, monitoring, and evaluating research outputs in Horizon Europe**. By integrating these services using the OSTrails Interoperability Frameworks for DMP platforms, Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and FAIR assessment tools and grounding them in input from Horizon Europe projects, the report demonstrates how **OpenAIRE's adoption of the OSTrails Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) Framework** can deliver scalable, policy-aligned, and machine-actionable solutions.

While the PTA vision for this report ultimately supports the broader enhancement of research output evaluation, including enriching CORDIS with contextual references and assessing deposited datasets against FAIR principles, **this first version focuses specifically on the evaluation of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) to support funders' monitoring and assessment needs**. Subsequent work will expand on the other PTA dimensions and services.

This report presents a **new, integrated approach to Data Management Plans (DMPs)** that improves their relevance, usability, and evaluation across the research lifecycle to ensure that the proposed improvements are both aligned with policy goals and technically feasible to implement. Grounded in real user needs, they provide a coherent foundation for advancing research data management across Europe at conceptual, technical and operational levels. The work focuses on three core areas:

- **Horizon Europe DMP Template:** Through targeted community feedback, the report identifies key usability challenges, role mismatches, and conceptual gaps in the current template. This informed the creation of a revised version that better supports researchers, research support staff, and funders in aligning planning with policy and practice.
- **DMP Evaluation:** Building on the D3.1 DMP Evaluation Rubric and Service Specifications [1], OSTrails validated essential dimensions for structured and semi-automated evaluation. Surveys conducted with the consortium and funders from 13 countries shaped a set of benchmarks and tests, now integrated in the beta version of the OSTrails evaluation service.
- **Machine-Actionable DMPs (maDMPs):** The report introduces the first version of the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile, designed to align with Horizon Europe requirements while supporting funders' monitoring needs. It adheres to the RDA DMP Common Standard and enables interoperability for exporting and using structured DMPs across systems.

Together, these outputs offer a coherent and practical approach to improving the quality of Data Management Plans (DMPs), aligning planning with FAIR and Open Science principles, and supporting funders in evaluating and monitoring research data management (RDM). While this deliverable draws on the Horizon Europe pilot led by OpenAIRE, because of its unique role in supporting project reporting to the European Commission via the OpenAIRE Graph, it reflects a broader collaborative effort. The solutions presented are grounded in the OSTrails Architecture and Interoperability Frameworks, developed with service providers across the project, and are designed to be adaptable to different contexts.

Each of the 24 pilots led by different partners will apply these shared frameworks according to their national, institutional, or thematic needs, configuring the services they onboard accordingly. The Horizon Europe pilot offers an early, concrete example of how the frameworks can be adopted and adapted in practice. Its experience helps inform and inspire the ongoing work across other pilots, which will further validate and extend these results within their respective settings.

1. Introduction

Research funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme requires Data Management Plans (DMPs) as a policy compliance mechanism and a vehicle for structured, FAIR-aligned planning across data and other research outputs. However, practical and technical gaps in template design, role assignment, and evaluation consistency have created significant burdens for researchers and funders alike. As the European Commission begins planning for the next Framework Programme (FP10), there is a critical need for actionable insights that link DMP policies with implementation realities.

OSTrails contributes to this transformation at conceptual, technical and operational levels by combining evidence from national funders, diverse Research Data Management (RDM) contexts, and RDM services. The project is developing an integrated, machine-actionable, and forward-compatible DMP framework. By aligning evaluation criteria, enhancing template structure, and extending the RDA DMP Common Standard, this deliverable lays the foundation for a next-generation approach to research data management that is actionable, role-aware, and fit for the evolving research ecosystem.

This deliverable focuses on the work performed under the **Horizon Europe pilot** which is one of several pilots under OSTrails that test and validate the proposed framework across national and thematic contexts. It is led by **OpenAIRE**, building on its long-standing collaboration with the European Commission and leveraging its infrastructure to support more effective research planning and monitoring in its Framework Programmes. At the core of this pilot is the implementation of the **OSTrails Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) Framework**, which connects three OpenAIRE services:

- **ARGOS** for structured, machine-actionable DMPs,
- The **OpenAIRE Graph** for continuous project and output tracking,
- The **Metadata Validator** for assessing data against FAIR principles [2].

The OpenAIRE Graph already connects to machine actionable DMPs published via ARGOS [3] and is directly integrated with the EC portal, providing near real-time updates on project information and research outputs. This trusted connection ensures that DMP evaluations can be grounded in the latest available data, improving the transparency, consistency, and scalability of research monitoring across Horizon Europe projects. Ultimately, it all comes down to offering a scalable, policy-aligned path toward improved monitoring and evaluation of research practices across the research project lifecycle.

This deliverable provides first evidence of the OSTrails Horizon Europe pilot activities to improve the quality, consistency, and interoperability of **Data Management Plans** by adopting the D1.4 OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1 [4]. The activities integrate three strands of evidence:

1. Survey validation of **evaluation dimensions** (building on deliverable D3.1).
2. Community feedback on the **usability and completeness of the [current Horizon Europe DMP template](#)**, including dedicated Horizon Europe Focus Group meetings.
3. Input influencing the design of a shared **OSTrails maDMP Application Profile** for Horizon Europe and national funders based on identified requirements.

Drawing on these three interrelated activities, we ensure that the resulting outputs, namely, a revised Horizon Europe DMP template, a structured maDMP Application Profile, and benchmarks and metrics of the evaluation service supporting automation, are grounded in real-world needs and are technically and operationally feasible.

Below we present the sections that together set the foundation for a coherent redesign of Data Management Plan practices under Horizon Europe:

- **Section 2** outlines the methodology used to collect and analyse data through template mapping, stakeholder engagement, and profile development.
- **Section 3** presents an integrated analysis of the survey responses, community feedback, and technical needs that shape the new maDMP profile.
- **Section 4** summarises key findings from each evidence stream.
- **Section 5** offers recommendations for improving the HE DMP template, enabling semi-automated evaluation, and applying the application profile.
- **Section 6** presents the key outcomes of the OSTrails PTA Framework and outlines next steps for pilot testing, stakeholder engagement, EOSC integration, and policy uptake towards FP10.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the methodological approach used to design and validate the proposed improvements to Horizon Europe DMP practices. It is structured around the three analytical strands introduced in Section 1: stakeholder engagement through surveys and workshops, desk research on DMP standards and practices, and the iterative design that will inform the OSTrails machine-actionable DMP profile.

2.1 Desk Research

To ground the redesign of the Horizon Europe DMP template in current standards and real-world practices, we conducted two complementary desk research activities.

First, we **mapped Horizon Europe and national funder DMP templates against the RDA DMP Common Standard**. This comparative analysis covered content elements, roles, lifecycle stages, and metadata or policy fields. The objectives were to:

- Identify semantic overlaps and gaps across templates.
- Determine where funder requirements exceed the current capabilities of the DMP Common Standard.
- Align key concepts such as “outputs,” “infrastructure,” and “licensing” with machine-readable properties.

Second, we **manually reviewed a random sample of Horizon Europe DMPs submitted to CORDIS** available in the OpenAIRE Graph to observe how researchers interpret and apply the existing HE template in practice. This analysis focused on common structural patterns, variations in content, and recurring ambiguities.

Together, these activities provided critical input for the **structural redesign of the Horizon Europe DMP template** to make it more consistent, usable, and aligned with **machine-actionable DMP (maDMP)**. The findings helped define which elements need to be clarified, restructured, or made explicitly linkable to enable automation and interoperability.

2.2 Community Engagement

To ensure that the evaluation approach and the Horizon Europe DMP template redesign are informed by stakeholder needs and expectations, we engaged two key communities: service providers and funders (for evaluation logic), and researchers and research support staff (for template usability).

We first implemented a **two-step survey process** to validate and prioritise DMP evaluation dimensions:

- An **internal survey** was conducted during the OSTrails General Assembly in Athens with project partners, pilot participants, and service providers. It is built on the initial set of evaluation dimensions proposed in D3.1 (*DMP Evaluation Rubric and Service Specifications*), asking respondents to classify each indicator as *Required*, *Nice to have*, or *Not relevant* for implementation. This step helped refine the dimensions based on practical relevance and feasibility.
- An **external survey** was then distributed to national funders participating in OSTrails pilots. Funders were asked to assess each dimension as *Mandatory*, *Recommended*, or *Not relevant*, focusing not only on current policy but also on **future evaluation priorities** aligned with Open Science and FAIR principles.

This iterative process revealed where funders and implementers align, where their priorities diverge, and which dimensions require clarification or further discussion to support structured and semi-automated DMP evaluation.

In parallel, we carried out a series of **consultations focused on improving the structure and usability of the Horizon Europe DMP template**. These included interactive webinars and two dedicated Horizon Europe focus groups with researchers, data stewards, and technical service providers. Participants discussed recurring issues in completing DMPs, shared suggestions for improving clarity, structure, and workflows, and reacted to early design concepts.

Insights from these sessions shaped the revised template structure, ensuring it better reflects actual research workflows, clarifies stakeholder roles, and lays the groundwork for alignment with machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) profiles.

2.3 Application Profile Design

The last methodological step involved crucial input informing the iterative design of the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile that is currently underway in collaboration with RDA DMP Common Standard (DCS) WG. Drawing on the evidence gathered from the previous activities, we proposed a set of additions and modifications to the RDA DCS to accommodate Horizon Europe and national policy needs.

The design process was carried out in collaboration with:

- Technical leads of SKG-DMP-FAIR assessment services.
- National pilot representatives, incl. data stewardship experts involved in infrastructure and workflow integration.

The profile design focused on:

- Enhancing structure and machine-actionability without breaking compatibility with the DCS.
- Supporting policy referencing, reproducibility metadata, and role-aware planning.
- Testing implementation in ARGOS for immediate feedback and validation on both the JSON and the evaluation.

The resulting profile, although in progress, enables a more interoperable, evaluable, and standards-aligned DMP practice suitable for future adoption.

3. Integrated Analysis of Evaluation Needs and maDMP Design

This section brings together the three core analytical inputs that underpin our work: (1) survey-based validation of maDMP evaluation dimensions [5], as a continuation of D3.1; (2) structured feedback on the current Horizon Europe DMP template; and (3) the development of a shared maDMP Application Profile based on those insights. The objective is to ensure that evaluation dimensions, policy needs, and technical structures align to support machine-actionable, FAIR-aligned DMP practices.

3.1. Survey Analysis

To support the design of a robust evaluation framework for maDMPs, we carried out two structured surveys: one addressed to OSTrails consortium members and pilot participants, and another to national funders. These efforts are built directly on the framework defined in Deliverable 3.1, which proposed a preliminary set of evaluation dimensions and metrics grounded in existing templates and rubrics. **Metrics** define *what is being measured* (e.g. machine-actionable licensing) and *how to assess it* in relation to a broader **Dimension** which serves as a *high-level evaluation area* (such as Coverage).

The consortium survey collected **33 responses** during the OSTrails General Assembly in Athens. As shown in **Table 1**, participants evaluated **28 metrics**, grouped into **4 core dimensions**.

Table 1. Dimensions, Metrics and Descriptions

DIMENSION	METRIC	DESCRIPTION
Completeness	Content Completeness	Checks if all required fields / all sections in the template(s) are filled.
Coverage	RDM Coverage	
	RDM Lifecycle Stages Addressed	Each phase of the data lifecycle (collection, processing, storage, sharing, preservation) is discussed.
	Budget for RDM	A data management budget is mentioned.
	Roles in RDM	Data Management responsibilities are clearly defined.
	Outputs Coverage	Confirms that each output is appropriately described (e.g. data type, format, repo, license, etc)
	Provenance	Confirms whether outputs are generated, collected, reused.
	Best Practices	Metadata standards, FAIR, Open etc
	Reproducibility	Confirms whether DMP includes qualified references to datasets, software, workflows, publications for reproducibility.

	Policy/ies Mentioned in DMP	Confirms that the specific funder/institutional/consortium policy/ies is/are cited in the DMP.
Feasibility	Input / Content Provided	Light cleaning of input data received in the DMP.
	Internal Consistency	Detects conflicting information in the DMP (e.g., data marked both "open" and "sensitive").
	Spelling Accuracy	Checks for misspellings in free-text fields such as abstract, names, or institution entries using a standard dictionary and contextual rules.
	Technical Capacity	Availability and operation of used resources.
	Repository Availability	Repository listed is online and accessible.
	Format-Repository Compatibility	Data formats are supported by the chosen repository.
	PID Resolution	Provided identifiers (DOIs, ORCIDs) resolve successfully.
	Access/Storage Location	Ensures storage and access provisions are legally compatible (e.g., EU-based storage for GDPR).
	Reproducibility	Light - Confirms whether there's mention of storing software, workflows, or provenance needed to reproduce results.
Compliance	Policy Compliance	Requirements in funder/national/institutional/consortium policy are addressed.
	Personal/Sensitive Data Handling	Checks whether the DMP includes statements on handling of personal data in line with legal frameworks (e.g., GDPR).
	National Policy	If needed, eg trade secrets
	Institutional Policy	Checks if processes referencing institutional services and workflows, are according to the institutional policy.
	Consortium Policy	Checks whether an RDM policy exists at the level of consortium practices, eg for shared services and project results such as survey results collected.
	Shared Infrastructure Used	Verifies that there is a shared infrastructure that is used for project results during research and / or for project management incl scientific purposes.
	Naming Convention Used	Verifies that there is a commonly agreed and followed naming convention in project's shared infrastructure.
	Data Sharing Timeline	Checks that timelines for data sharing match policy requirements (e.g., "no later than 6 months").

	Licensing	Verifies if licenses comply with policy-mandated openness (e.g., CC-BY for metadata).
	Data Formats	Verified if formats are open or proprietary.
	Embargo Period Specified	If data is restricted, ensures embargo end date is stated and within acceptable limits (e.g., < 12 months).
	Access Request Procedure Described	For non-open data, checks if there's a procedure for data access (e.g., request via repository or email).
	Access Condition Stated	Verifies that each dataset has an access condition defined (e.g., open, restricted, closed)
	Retention Period Specified	Confirms that the DMP includes a data retention period compliant with the policy (e.g., 10 years).
	Ethics Approval Referenced	If policy requires, confirms ethics approval or process is documented.
	Data Access Committee Declared	Confirms that a Data Access Committee or equivalent governance body is mentioned in the DMP, when needed.
	Repositories Interoperability	Checks if repositories meet the OpenAIRE guidelines.
	Use of Trusted Repositories	Checks if repositories meet the policy requirement (e.g., certified or listed in re3data/FAIRsharing).
	Persistent Identifiers Used	Ensures that PIDs are used for datasets, people, institutions, as mandated.
	Disciplinary Standards	Checks if the chosen metadata formats, ontologies, and repositories align with the research domain.
	Licensing	Verifies if licenses comply with policy-mandated openness (e.g., CC-BY for metadata).
	Reproducibility	According to policy; might differ depending on who enforces the policy and what it requires and / or encourages.
	DCS Compliance	Structure follows the DMP Common Standard.
	DCS Fields	Checks if all required fields from the DMP Common Standard are filled.
	DCS Extension Fields	Checks if additional required fields from templates or policies are included.
	Machine-Actionable Format	Verifies if the DMP is submitted in a machine-actionable format.

Each dimension was rated as "Required for compliance," "Nice to have," or "Not relevant." Key patterns observed in the consortium data include:

- **High** consensus around Content Completeness, PID Resolution, Outputs Coverage, and Repository Availability.

- **Moderate** support for RDM Lifecycle, Reproducibility, and Policy references.
- **Lower** priority given to feasibility-related indicators like Technical Capacity and Spelling Accuracy.

Of them, the majority of respondents found **content completeness** as “Required for compliance,” indicating strong agreement on the need for comprehensive DMP content.

Figure 1. Content Completeness results based on survey responses from the OSTrails General Assembly in Athens.

Respondents considered **Outputs Coverage, Provenance, Best Practices,** and **RDM Lifecycle** elements like **Roles** and **Budget** to be important. These were mostly rated as either **Required for compliance** or **Nice to have**, showing strong agreement on the need to include them in DMPs. Very few considered any of these aspects irrelevant, indicating strong support for comprehensive, structured coverage of data management in DMPs, particularly in aspects that directly affect implementation, transparency, and reusability.

Figure 2. Coverage results based on survey responses from the OSTrails General Assembly in Athens.

Respondents identified **PID Resolution** and **Repository Availability** as the most critical **feasibility** aspects in a DMP. **Internal Consistency** and **Access/Storage Location** were also seen as important. Other aspects like **Technical Capacity** and **Spelling Accuracy** were rated lower, suggesting they're less central to evaluation.

Figure 3. Feasibility results based on survey responses from the OSTrails General Assembly in Athens.

The majority of respondents rated most **compliance-related elements** as either **Required for compliance** or **Nice to have**, showing broad agreement on their relevance in DMP evaluation.

- **Machine-actionable format, Policy compliance, Reproducibility, PID usage, and Access-related fields** (e.g. conditions, request procedures) were most often marked as **Required**.
- **DCS fields, Trusted repositories, Retention periods, and Data formats** were also seen as important, but with more mixed ratings.
- **Consortium, institutional, and national policies** as well as **naming conventions** and **shared infrastructure** received the highest **Not relevant** ratings, suggesting limited priority across respondents.

This distribution indicates a preference for core compliance aspects that affect data accessibility and transparency, with less emphasis on institutional or technical context.

Figure 4. Compliance results based on survey responses from the OSTrails General Assembly in Athens.

This first analysis helped prioritise, refine and redistribute elements of the initial 4 dimensions into a second version of the survey that clearly reflects **FAIR and Open dimensions and metrics**. The resulting **6 dimensions** and **25 metrics** were shared across the project’s pilots relevant national funders.

Table 2. Dimension, Description of the dimension, Metric and Description of the metric

DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION OF THE DIMENSION	METRIC	DESCRIPTION OF THE METRIC
Completeness	Evaluates whether the DMP is fully filled in, covering all required sections without missing content.	Content Completeness	
RDM Coverage	Assesses how thoroughly the DMP addresses data management across the full lifecycle, project roles, and types of outputs.	RDM Lifecycle Stages Addressed	Ensures all phases of data management are discussed.
		Budget for RDM	Verifies the inclusion of a dedicated data management budget.

		Roles in RDM	Confirms assignment of data management responsibilities.
		Outputs Coverage	Ensures that each research output is described in terms of type, format, repository, etc.
		Best Practices Coverage	Checks for references to standards, FAIR principles, and openness.
		Reproducibility	Ensures that outputs are linked to resources enabling reproducibility.
		Policy/ies Mentioned in DMP	Confirms relevant data policies are cited.
		Ethics Approval Referenced	Confirms that ethical review processes are acknowledged if required.
		Repositories Interoperability	Verifies that repositories meet expected standards (e.g., OpenAIRE guidelines), per policy.
Feasibility	Measures how realistic and internally consistent the DMP is, including technical, legal, and practical considerations.	Input / Content Provided	Checks for usable and coherent content.
		Internal Consistency	Detects contradictory information within the plan.
		Technical Capacity	Assesses availability and readiness of

			infrastructure and tools.
		Repository Availability	Confirms repositories are accessible and active.
		Format-Repository Compatibility	Ensures data formats are accepted by chosen repositories.
		PID Resolution	Validates functionality of persistent identifiers.
		Access/Storage Location	Confirms storage locations comply with regulations like GDPR.
		Reproducibility	Confirms that steps are in place for storing reusable resources.
FAIRness	Evaluates how well the DMP and associated research outputs follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).	FAIR DMP	Checks if the DMP itself is published with a license and PID.
		FAIR Datasets	Ensures datasets follow FAIR principles.
		FAIR Software	Ensures software follows FAIR principles.
		FAIR-enabling Repository	Verifies the use of repositories supporting FAIR principles.
		FAIR-enabling Services	Confirms services used support FAIR workflows and standards.
Openness	Focuses on how open the research outputs and their	Licensing	Verifies that outputs are published under open licenses (e.g.,

	documentation are, assessing whether the project follows open science best practices.		CC-BY), promoting reuse.
		Access Condition Stated	Ensures access levels (open/restricted/closed) are declared for each dataset.
		Embargo Period Specified	Confirms any temporary restrictions are time-bound and justified.
		Access Request Procedure Described	For non-open data, confirms a clear access mechanism is in place.
		Data Formats	Ensures the use of open, machine-readable, and non-proprietary formats.
		Access protocol	Ensures the use of open exchange protocols.
Policy	Confirms that funder/institutional /consortium/national policies are referenced and followed. This dimension combines metrics from previous dimensions to reflect the funder's policies.	National Policy	Confirms compliance with national-level requirements (e.g., trade secrets, national repositories).
		Institutional Policy	Ensures DMP aligns with institutional workflows, tools, and rules.
		Consortium Policy	Checks for the presence of consortium-level data management practices or agreements, such as

			shared infrastructure or naming conventions used.
		Personal/Sensitive Data Handling	Verifies GDPR or similar frameworks are followed for personal data.
DCS Compliance	Checks whether the DMP is structured according to the technical standard defined by the DMP Common Standard (DCS) for machine-actionability and interoperability.	DCS Compliance	Validates that the DMP is available as machine actionable (ma)DMP.

From those, the survey was completed by **16 national funders representing 13 countries**¹ involved in the OSTrails pilots (See **Figure 5**).

¹ Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ), LifeWatch ERIC, NWO, FCT| FCCN, Research Council of Norway, Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS), TA CR, Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, Research council of Finland, RWTH Aachen University Library, HEAL-Link / Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Agence nationale de la recherche, CDTI, FECYT (Spanish foundation for science and technology) and Research Ireland. The Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research responded via email only.

Figure 5. National Pilot Countries and Survey Responses

National funders were asked to classify each dimension as "Mandatory," "Recommended," or "Not Relevant" according either to their current policy or to their preferences for future adoption. Their responses show strong prioritisation of Content Completeness, DMP Common Standard (DCS) Compliance and Openness. Specifically, all respondents agreed that DMPs should be evaluated for **content completeness** ensuring that required sections are not left blank or underdeveloped.

Figure 6. Completeness assessment results based on survey responses.

8. Completeness

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

All funders supported verifying whether DMPs are structured in a machine-actionable format and aligned with the **DMP Common Standard**.

Figure 7. DCS Compliance assessment results based on survey responses.

14. DCS Compliance

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

DCS Compliance: Validates that the DMP is available as machine actionable (ma)DMP.

Nearly all measures under the Openness dimension were rated as important, particularly:

- **Embargo period** justification
- **Access request** procedures
- Use of **open licenses/access conditions**

Figure 8. Openness assessment results based on survey responses.

12. Openness

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

Licensing: Verifies that outputs are published under open licenses (e.g., CC-BY), promoting reuse.

Access Condition Stated: Ensures access levels (open/restricted/closed) are declared for each dataset.

Embargo Period Specified: Confirms any temporary restrictions are time-bound and justified.

Access Request Procedure Described: For non-open data, confirms a clear access mechanism is in place.

Data Formats: Ensures the use of open, machine-readable, and non-proprietary formats.

Access protocol: Ensures the use of open exchange protocols.

In terms of **RDM Coverage**, most funders supported evaluating DMPs based on how well they address key activities in the research data lifecycle, including data collection, storage, preservation, and access.

Figure 9. RDM Coverage assessment results based on survey responses.

9. RDM Coverage

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

- RDM Lifecycle Stages Addressed:** Ensures all phases of data management are discussed.
- Budget for RDM:** Verifies the inclusion of a dedicated data management budget.
- Roles in RDM:** Confirms assignment of data management responsibilities.
- Outputs Coverage:** Ensures that each research output is described in terms of type, format, repository, etc.
- Best Practices Coverage:** Checks for references to standards, FAIR principles, and openness.
- Reproducibility:** Ensures that outputs are linked to resources enabling reproducibility.
- Policy/ies Mentioned in DMP:** Confirms relevant data policies are cited.
- Ethics Approval Referenced:** Confirms that ethical review processes are acknowledged if required.
- Repositories Interoperability:** Verifies that repositories meet expected standards (e.g., OpenAIRE guidelines), per policy.

Among the various FAIR-related metrics, the most selected were:

- Whether the **DMP itself is FAIR** (i.e the DMP has a license, is assigned a PID, etc)
- Whether **datasets are described to support FAIR principles**
- Whether a **FAIR-enabling repository** is chosen

Figure 10. FAIRness assessment results based on survey responses.

11. FAIRness

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

- FAIR DMP:** Checks if the DMP itself is published with a license and PID.
- FAIR Datasets:** Ensures datasets follow FAIR principles.
- FAIR Software:** Ensures software follows FAIR principles.
- FAIR-enabling Repository:** Verifies the use of repositories supporting FAIR principles.
- FAIR-enabling Services:** Confirms services used support FAIR workflows and standards.

Next, the Policy dimension highlighted strong consensus over **National, Institutional and topical/thematic policy compliance. Consortium** policy alignment were considered “Nice to have” or “Important for future inclusion.”

Figure 11. Policy assessment results based on survey responses.

13. Policy

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

- National Policy:** Confirms compliance with national-level requirements (e.g., trade secrets, national repositories).
- Institutional Policy:** Ensures DMP aligns with institutional workflows, tools, and rules.
- Consortium Policy:** Checks for the presence of consortium-level data management practices or agreements, such as shared...
- Personal/Sensitive Data Handling:** Verifies GDPR or similar frameworks are followed for personal data.

Funders largely agreed that DMPs must demonstrate practical viability. Criteria such as repository availability, PID resolution, and input coherence were frequently marked as “Required,” highlighting expectations for functional infrastructure and usable, consistent content. While some aspects like technical capacity and format-repository compatibility were seen as “Nice to have” or “Not relevant” by a few, the overall emphasis was on ensuring DMPs are not only policy-compliant but also realistically implementable.

Figure 12. Feasibility assessment results based on survey responses.

10. Feasibility

[More details](#)

● Required ● Not Required, but nice to have ● Not relevant

- Input / Content Provided:** Checks for usable and coherent content.
- Internal Consistency:** Detects contradictory information within the plan.
- Technical Capacity:** Assesses availability and readiness of infrastructure and tools.
- Repository Availability:** Confirms repositories are accessible and active.
- Format-Repository Compatibility:** Ensures data formats are accepted by chosen repositories.
- PID Resolution:** Validates functionality of persistent identifiers.
- Access/Storage Location:** Confirms storage locations comply with regulations like GDPR.
- Reproducibility:** Confirms that steps are in place for storing reusable resources.

The comparative analysis of the two surveys shows alignment on core evaluation categories but also reveals differences in emphasis. Consortium participants placed more attention on planning realism and support for diverse research workflows. Funders focused on structured compliance monitoring and automation readiness. These seven high-priority dimensions that resulted are currently being formalised in the [DMP Evaluation Service](#), that is co-developed with ARC and operated by TU Wien.

3.2. Feedback on the HE Template

The second line of analysis focused on identifying real-world challenges in completing and further exploiting Data Management Plans (DMPs) using the Horizon Europe template. Structured input was gathered through a combination of pilot discussions, thematic webinars, and stakeholder consultations involving researchers, data stewards, and institutional support staff. To complement this, a review of 100 randomly selected Horizon Europe DMPs available via CORDIS and the OpenAIRE Graph was conducted.

The findings reveal recurring challenges that fall into three broad categories: **structural limitations**, **content-related gaps**, and **technical barriers**.

3.2.1. Structural Limitations

- **Fragmented and Redundant Layout:** The template lacks a clear structural overview or introductory section. Reviewers must reconstruct context from scattered responses, which impairs both human readability and automated analysis.
- **Ambiguity and Inconsistency:** Submitted DMPs vary significantly in how template sections are interpreted and filled. Some content is misplaced, sections are partially completed or omitted, and formatting is inconsistent. These issues were evident in the full-text review of the 100 DMPs.
- **Lack of Structured Inputs:** Most fields are free text only, including those asking for critical information such as repository names, license terms, file formats, and data access conditions. This results in inconsistent responses that cannot be automatically parsed, validated, or linked to other systems.

3.2.2. Content-Related Gaps

- **Role Misalignment:** The template often requires researchers to provide information that falls outside their expertise (e.g. backup procedures, repository certification, long-term preservation), leading to vague or speculative answers that reduce plan quality.
- **Insufficient Support for Software and Other Research Outputs:** The template is heavily data-centric and lacks space or guidance for other research outputs such as software, workflows, models, or simulations—even though the grant agreement explicitly mentions "tools and instruments" required for data reuse.
- **Missing Elements: Versioning, Unused Data, and Data Disposal:** Several key aspects of data lifecycle management are not addressed:
 - **Data versioning** is not mentioned.
 - There is no prompt to declare **data that will not be reused or shared**.

- **Secure data deletion** after the retention period, especially for sensitive or personal data, is not covered.

3.2.3. Technical and Interoperability Barriers

- **Not Machine-Actionable:** DMPs are typically submitted as narrative documents (e.g. PDFs) using a question-and-answer format that generates unstructured text. This limits their interoperability, makes automated validation infeasible, and prevents integration with systems such as institutional CRIS or EOSC related tools.
- **Non-standardised Vocabulary and Metadata:** Repository names, license terms, and access conditions are written in prose without using standard vocabularies. This makes it difficult to verify compliance (e.g., whether a trusted repository is used or whether licensing terms are FAIR-compliant) and undermines machine-actionability.

These findings were further substantiated by the review of 100 [Horizon Europe DMPs available in CORDIS](#), which illustrated the broad variation in how the template is applied. In particular, the review highlighted inconsistencies in formatting, incomplete responses, and diverse interpretations of the template structure. The following figures provide a visual summary of these observations.

Figure 13 groups DMPs into five structural types: those using the Horizon Europe template with all guiding questions; those with the same template but incomplete or partially filled sections; those following the Horizon Europe table of contents without including the questions; those focused only on specific elements such as licensing, repository, and dataset information; and those written as unstructured, narrative-only text.

Figure 13. Different Types of DMPs' structure & content

Figure 14 shows how these structural types often overlap, revealing frequent cases of hybrid or inconsistently completed DMPs. This further complicates interpretation and evaluation, especially when key sections are missing or formats are mixed within a single plan.

Figure 14. Combination of DMPs' structure & content per type

3.3. Horizon Europe Requirements for the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile

The third input into the analysis focuses on the technical and semantic design of the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile (AP). This work builds directly on the evidence gathered through the survey analysis (3.1) and template feedback (3.2) and aims to implement their insights into a shared, machine-actionable structure.

The profile extends the RDA DMP Common Standard to:

- Address the seven validated evaluation dimensions (e.g. completeness, openness, FAIRness);
- Provide structured support for Horizon Europe and national funder policies.
- Accommodate in the DMP structure the distinction between intentions and implementation actions described in different stages of the project lifecycle.
- Enable role attribution and semantic linking across datasets, outputs, and plans.

It introduces new DMP and dataset entities filling known gaps in existing templates, taking the Horizon Europe as an example along with Science Europe DMP guidelines followed by the OSTrails' pilots. In this part, we summarize the needs for inclusion in OSTrails AP coming from analysis of Horizon Europe DMP and its potential to semi-automate evaluation.

3.3.1. New Entity: related identifiers

A new related identifier entity shall support **qualified references** within DMPs, as required by the Horizon Europe template. Funders increasingly expect DMPs to include persistent, structured links to related projects, datasets, publications, software, and policies at both the DMP and dataset levels.

Table 3. Related Identifiers entities in the OSTrails Application Profile

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
related_identifiers	Provides links between outputs, actors, and activities	Nested Data Structure	0..*	876543
related_identifiers/identifier	Specific value of an identifier	String	1	10.5281/zenodo.12345
related_identifiers/identifierType	Type of the identifier	Controlled Vocabulary	1	DOI
related_identifiers/relationType	Relationship between the linked elements	Controlled Vocabulary	0..1	IsDocumentedBy

By defining related identifier as a standalone, reusable structure, the maDMP can:

- Represent qualified references clearly and consistently
- Avoid duplication across DMP and dataset sections
- Enable automated integration with PID infrastructures (e.g., DataCite, OpenAIRE Graph, RAID, RO-Crate, repository infrastructures, ...)

Each related identifier includes: identifier (e.g., DOI or URL); identifier_type (e.g., DOI, Handle); relation_type (e.g., *IsDocumentedBy*, *IsDerivedFrom*, *Cites*)

It is used under both: dmp.related_identifier[] AND dataset.related_identifier[]

3.3.2. New DMP entities and properties

To support more robust, transparent, and machine-actionable DMPs, we identified the need for several enhancements to the `dmp` entity. These updates are aligned with requirements from Horizon Europe, funder templates such as the Science Europe DMP Evaluation Rubric, and ongoing dialogue with pilot initiatives, including collaboration with the TIER2 project on reproducibility-focused planning.

Table 4. DMP entities

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
<code>dmp/dmp_status</code>	Indicates the lifecycle stage of the DMP	String	1	draft
<code>dmp/contributor/role</code>	Role of each contributor in relation to the DMP	Controlled Vocabulary	1..*	Data Steward
<code>dmp/contact/affiliation</code>	Organisation or unit affiliated with the main DMP contact	Nested Structure	0..*	Athena Research Center
<code>dmp/contributor/affiliation</code>	Organisation or unit affiliated with a DMP contributor	Nested Structure	0..*	CNR

These additions provide:

- Lifecycle metadata to distinguish between draft, active, and final versions
- Institutional context for contributors and main contacts
- Role attribution using controlled vocabularies such as DataCite instead of the initial string

We introduce a dedicated policies entity to represent legal, ethical, contractual, and institutional policies that govern research activities. While Horizon Europe addresses this under Section 7 ("Other Issues"), current maDMP models lack a structured way to declare and describe applicable policies.

Table 5. Policy entity

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
<code>policies/title</code>	Name of the applicable policy	String	1	TUWien Open Science Policy
<code>policies/description</code>	Short explanation of the policy's	String	0..1	Describes institutional

	purpose or relevance			RDM obligations
policies/policy_type	Type of policy (e.g. legal, ethical, institutional)	Controlled Vocabulary	1	institutional
policies/jurisdiction	Geographic or organizational scope of the policy	String	0..1	European Union
policies/related_identifiers	Qualified references to the policy (e.g. PID, URL)	Nested Data Structure	0..*	10.5281/zenodo.98765

By defining *policy* as a nested entity of the *dmp*, we enable:

- Standardised and auditable references to applicable frameworks (e.g. GDPR, institutional mandates).
- Automated policy checks.
- Connections to datasets, licences, and access conditions using `related_identifier[]`.

To treat the DMP as a FAIR digital object, we introduce a new **dmp_license** nested data structure. While the RDA DMP Common Standard includes licenses for datasets, it lacks a way to declare the license governing the use of the DMP itself.

Table 6. License property in the DMP entity

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
dmp_license/license_ref	Reference to the license applied to the DMP	URI	1	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
dmp_license/start_date	Date from which the license is valid	Date (ISO 8601)	0..1	2024-03-01
dmp_license/access_rights	Access level of the DMP content	Controlled Vocabulary	1	open

These additions enable:

- Clear declaration of whether the DMP is **openly licensed** (e.g. CC BY) or shared under **restricted terms**
- Representation of **access conditions** in alignment with Zenodo, OpenAIRE, and DataCite practices

- Structured support for DMP sharing, citation, and reuse across institutional and funder platforms

3.3.3. New dataset entities and properties

To improve dataset planning, traceability, and reuse, we introduce several **new properties** within the dataset entity. These address key gaps in representing dataset lifecycle, audience, and generation methodology.

Table 7. New properties in the Dataset entity

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
dataset/dataset_status	Indicates the lifecycle stage of the dataset	String	1	completed
dataset/target_audience	Intended audience or relevance of the dataset	String	0..1	researchers, policy_makers
dataset/methodology	Reference to a methodology object describing data generation	Nested Data Structure	0..1	Linked method object

The dataset/methodology field enables qualified references and structured descriptions of how data was collected, processed, or derived.

Table 8. Methodology property in the Dataset entity

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
methodology/description	Description of the method, procedure, or workflow	String	1	Survey with sampling design
methodology/methodology_id	Object Describing the methodology identifier	Nested Structure	1	
methodology/methodology_id/identifier	Identifier for the methodology artifact (e.g. a PID)	String	1	10.5281/zenodo.67890
methodology/methodology_id/type	To specify a type of an identifier for a methodology.	Controlled Vocabulary	1	doi

These additions enable:

- Lifecycle tracking of datasets (e.g. planned, completed, withdrawn)
- Clear documentation of intended reuse communities
- Qualified references to workflows or methods using PIDs, improving reproducibility and transparency

NEW PROPERTY UNDER DATASET DISTRIBUTION

To complement policy-aware planning and improve transparency in data sharing practices, we introduce one new property within the distribution entity. This addition allows data providers to **explicitly describe restrictions** on open access, aligning with requirements from Horizon Europe and recommendations from the Science Europe DMP Evaluation Rubric.

Table 9. New property in the distribution entity

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	CARDINALITY	EXAMPLE VALUE
distribution/restriction_explanation	Describes the reason why the dataset cannot be shared openly	String	0..1	Contains personal data under GDPR

This addition enables:

- Transparent justification of restrictions placed on open data sharing
- Improved alignment with funder expectations for openness, while allowing exceptions
- Structured evaluation of data access decisions and their legal or ethical basis

These maDMP additions respond directly to the needs and gaps surfaced by stakeholders, they are forward-compatible and align with the RDA DMP Common Standard to ensure interoperability across platforms.

4. Findings

The findings presented in this section synthesise the key outcomes from each of the three analytical strands described in [Section 3](#). They go beyond surface-level observations to articulate what the results mean for improving DMP practices under Horizon Europe. Each subsection captures one of the main lines of evidence, i.e. evaluation dimensions, template feedback, and application profile design, and sets the stage for the concrete recommendations and preliminary outputs that follow in [Section 5](#).

4.1. Insights from Survey-Based Evaluation

Dimension Validation

The analysis of responses from **16 national funders and 33 consortium stakeholders** confirms strong alignment on seven core evaluation dimensions identified in OSTrails: **Content Completeness, RDM Coverage, Feasibility, Openness, FAIRness, Policy Compliance, and DCS (machine-actionable format) Compliance**. These dimensions reflect shared expectations across roles and national contexts, validating the direction of the OSTrails framework.

Key findings include:

- **Universal endorsement of Content Completeness:** All funders agreed that DMPs must cover all mandatory sections. Consortium respondents echoed this, with 70% selecting this as “Required for compliance.”
- **Strong demand for machine-actionable structure:** DCS Compliance was rated highly across both groups, confirming the importance of aligning DMPs with the DMP Common Standard for automation.
- **Openness as a top-tier dimension:** Nearly all funders prioritised openness-related indicators (e.g. access conditions, embargo periods, licensing), aligning with consortium feedback that also elevated PID resolution and repository availability.
- **Mixed views on feasibility and implementation aspects:** Metrics such as repository backup practices, spelling accuracy, or storage technicalities received lower priority, especially from funders. However, institutional support roles viewed these as essential for internal workflows.
- **Emerging interest in consortium-wide planning:** Though not yet formalised in most national policies, funders indicated growing interest in capturing shared infrastructure, policy alignment, and collaborative decision-making within consortia.
- **Alignment with FAIR and policy-aware planning:** Metrics linked to metadata quality, repository certification, and policy references were strongly supported, confirming a collective shift toward more structured, transparent research data planning.

4.2. Feedback on the Horizon Europe DMP Template

Stakeholder engagement through webinars and document reviews surfaced critical gaps in the current Horizon Europe DMP template and its practical implementation.

Key insights include:

- **Role mismatch is a systemic issue:** Researchers are frequently asked to complete questions that should fall under the responsibility of data stewards, legal advisors, or IT departments. This creates inefficiencies and reduces data quality.
- **Free-text structure undermines reuse and automation:** The current template's flexibility results in fragmented formats, with a mix of questions, tables, and headings used inconsistently across submissions. A review of 100 HE DMPs revealed incomplete sections, narrative-only responses, and limited metadata fields.
- **Lack of policy and infrastructure linkage:** Fields for declaring applicable policies, repository conditions, or data access workflows are either missing or too vague to support evaluation or reuse.
- **Need for Lifecycle-Aware Structuring of DMPs:** There is a clear need to distinguish between DMP content required at the start of a project and content developed during its execution. Stakeholders overwhelmingly supported introducing a versioned structure, separating high-level declarations (suitable for funders) from detailed implementation (carried out post-award by support staff and services).

In parallel, key limitations were identified in how DMPs are currently reviewed. The use of high-level rubrics without operational indicators often results in inconsistent interpretation across evaluators. The absence of shared scoring rules or reviewer training introduces subjectivity, while narrative-based reviews and checklists lack machine-actionability and comparability. As a result, feedback tends to be vague and difficult to act on (e.g. "add more detail"), limiting its value for improving alignment with FAIR principles. Finally, current workflows do not support collaborative or role-based review (e.g. joint input from funders, data stewards, or legal experts), making comprehensive evaluation difficult.

These findings support the transition toward role-aware, machine-actionable templates and highlight the importance of aligning evaluation, planning, and institutional practices.

4.3. Requirements for the OSTrails Common Application Profile

The findings from the surveys and template analysis directly informed this preliminary development of the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile, which introduces structural, semantic, and policy-aware enhancements to the RDA DMP Common Standard.

Key profile requirements include:

- **Staged DMP content model:** The profile structures DMP content across versions, distinguishing high-level “Declarations” from detailed “Implementations” through field grouping and use of the `relatedIdentifier` structure to connect them.
- **Role attribution and contributor affiliation:** New properties were proposed to reflect who is responsible for what (e.g. researcher, data steward, legal officer) making the DMP a collaborative document.
- **Representation of full research data lifecycle:** Fields such as `dataset_status`, `dataset_distribution.restriction_explanation`, and `dataset.methodology` address planning across collection, sharing, preservation, and reuse phases.
- **Policy referencing and reproducibility:** Dedicated entities support linking to applicable policies (GDPR, institutional mandates) and describing methodological reproducibility using persistent identifiers.
- **Enhanced metadata and licensing transparency:** Support for DMP-level licensing (`dmp.license_ref`, `license_access_rights`) allows the plan itself to be treated as a FAIR object and reused.
- **Compatibility and extensibility:** All additions are forward-compatible with the RDA DMP Common Standard, ensuring interoperability across systems while addressing Horizon Europe and national funder needs.

Overall, a number of structural limitations remain in the current version of the DCS. Notably, it does not represent the full research data lifecycle, omitting key stages like data collection, processing, and intermediate analysis. It also lacks the ability to distinguish between different DMP states (e.g. draft, active, final), which is essential for tracking updates and implementation. Moreover, DCS does not capture relationships between the DMP and other components such as reproducibility plans, RDM systems, or infrastructure used. There is no structured way to include policy references, nor alignment with FAIR metrics or implementation verification. These gaps significantly constrain its use for semi-automated evaluation and comprehensive RDM planning.

5. Recommendations for HE projects

Building on the validated dimensions, community feedback, and technical profile design, this section provides targeted recommendations for improving Data Management Plan practices under Horizon Europe. Each subsection corresponds to one of the three main outputs of the OSTrails work: the revision of the HE DMP template, the design on benchmarks and metrics to feed the DMP evaluation service that is underway, and the adoption of a machine-actionable DMP application profile. Together, these recommendations aim to streamline planning, enable structured evaluation, and ensure alignment with FAIR and policy requirements.

5.1. Revised DMP Template for FP10

To address structural and usability limitations identified, we recommend implementing a redesigned Horizon Europe DMP template that separates responsibilities and aligns with automation goals.

Key actions include:

- Introduce a **staged DMP content model** to distinguish between declarations (for funders) and implementation details (for institutional actors).
- Support **reuse across projects** by allowing declarative sections to be linked or imported from previous DMPs using persistent references.
- **Align sections with stakeholder roles**, ensuring that questions related to infrastructure, preservation, or legal compliance can be completed by data stewards, librarians or other expert support staff.
- Replace free-text boxes with **structured fields that align with the DCS** for key components such as policies, repositories, licenses to capture and export data according to maDMP.

This new design enhances the clarity, interoperability, and long-term value of DMPs in Horizon Europe projects. This includes restructuring into a staged content format (declarations vs. implementation), clarifying roles, and improving alignment with research workflows.

Table 10. Recommendations for Horizon Europe Template

HE TEMPLATE SECTION	RECOMMENDED ACTION(S)
Admin Info	<p>Add a structured cover page and an introduction</p> <p>Begin the DMP with a standardized cover section capturing key project metadata and DMP information. This cover page should include fields such as the project title, grant ID, acronym, project duration, contact person (data steward), and DMP version/date. Providing this summary in a structured format will facilitate tracking and referencing of the DMP. It will also enable automatic linking of the DMP to the project in EC systems.</p> <p>Add an Introduction Section: This overview should outline the project’s overall data management strategy and name the data manager. By making this a formal part of the template, FP10 DMPs would start with a clear summary, setting the scene for the detailed answers that follow.</p>
Dataset(s)	<p>Incorporate a Dataset Summary Table</p> <p>To reduce redundancy and improve clarity, require a dataset summary table early in the DMP. In this table, the project should list each dataset (or dataset collection) with key attributes in a tabular format. Columns include: dataset reference name, description, data type/format, estimated size, responsible partner, intended repository, access level (open/restricted), and license. This approach provides a one-glance overview of all datasets, which prevents scattered information. Implementing a similar summary in the FP10 template would mean that instead of writing repetitive descriptions in multiple sections, researchers fill out a structured inventory of datasets once. Reviewers can quickly see what data will be produced and how it will be managed. Moreover, this table can be made machine-readable (e.g. each row as a structured record).</p>
	<p>Address Data Versioning</p> <p>Incorporate prompts that ask projects to describe their versioning strategy for data (and code). For example, the template could include a question like: “How will you version control updates to your data and DMP? Will multiple versions of datasets be preserved, and how will</p>

	<p>changes be documented?” By including it, the DMP can capture whether a project will use version control systems (or new file versions with timestamps, etc. It also encourages teams to think about how their “living” DMP will reflect data changes through DMP revisions.</p> <p>A section on versioning will prompt best practices like assigning DOIs or PIDs to dataset versions and recording provenance metadata. This not only improves reproducibility (by enabling others to cite a specific version of a dataset) but also aligns with the notion that DMPs themselves should be versioned documents. The recommendation is to make versioning an expected topic in FP10 DMPs, so that projects plan from the start how they will handle data updates and ensure previous versions remain accessible if needed.</p>
	<p>Address Unused/Not shared Data</p> <p>Add a question or sub-section for unused data or data not to be shared. For example: “Will there be any data generated that you do not plan to use or share? This prompt would fill the gap where projects currently may drop data silently (e.g. incomplete experiments, low-quality data, or data with disclosure risks) without mention. Embedding this in the template ensures such cases are not forgotten. For reviewers and the Commission, these declarations provide clarity on what portion of data will remain private or will be destroyed (see section 4.8. below). It also ties into resource planning.</p>
	<p>Require Structured Licensing Metadata</p> <p>Improve how licensing information is captured by using standard labels or dropdown options for licenses. The FP10 template should prompt projects to specify under which license(s) data (and software) will be shared in a structured manner. Instead of a free-text answer about licensing, the template could, for example, have a checklist or menu of common open licenses (CC BY 4.0, CC0, MIT for software, etc.), along with an opportunity to explain any deviations.</p> <p>This supports directly the Horizon Europe mandate that data be shared under a CC BY licence or CC0 (or equivalent). By capturing a license name in a consistent</p>

	<p>format, it becomes easier to verify if the chosen license meets the “open” criterion and to enable discovery. Additionally, structured license metadata can be leveraged in EOSC – e.g. to filter datasets by license or to ensure that metadata harvested by OpenAIRE includes license info.</p>
<p>Security</p>	<p>Address Secure Data Deletion Practices</p> <p>Extend the template to cover data deletion and end-of-life plans. In projects dealing with sensitive or personal data, secure deletion is often a legal/ethical requirement once the data is no longer needed. Currently, DMPs seldom address this.</p> <p>By explicitly asking this question, the Commission ensures that consortia handling e.g. personal identifiable data or confidential data think about how to irreversibly erase that data when the time comes (e.g. using cryptographic wipe, DOD-standard overwriting, etc.). This not only protects participants and institutions, but it also demonstrates compliance with GDPR’s storage limitation principle.</p>
<p>Repository</p>	<p>Include a Repository Profile Section</p> <p>Expand the template to have a dedicated section where projects provide structured information about the repositories they will use. This repository profile should ask for: the repository name and URL, the repository type (institutional, domain-specific, general-purpose), and evidence of trustworthiness (e.g. certifications like CoreTrustSeal or whether it is an EOSC-federated resource). By collecting this in a uniform way, the DMP will directly address the Commission’s emphasis on “trusted repositories.” Currently, the requirement to use trusted repositories is often satisfied by a simple statement in the DMP, but without a standardized format or verification. By structuring this info, the Commission can more easily ensure compliance and gather statistics (e.g. what fraction of projects use certified repositories). It potentially also enables integration with the EOSC ecosystem.</p>
<p>Other Outputs</p>	<p>Add Dedicated Fields for Software and Other Research Outputs</p>

	<p>Update the template to explicitly address software and other research outputs. This could take the form of new questions or sections in the DMP, for example: “Will you produce research software or code? If yes, how will the software be managed and shared (repository, licence, documentation)?” Currently, such content is often missing or only briefly mentioned under data documentation. Treating software as a “first-class citizen” in the DMP signals its importance for reproducibility.</p>
<p>Policy</p>	<p>Add Dedicated Fields for Policies applied to the DMP</p> <p>This could include structured fields to list and describe applicable policies, such as funder requirements, institutional guidelines, national regulations, and international or European frameworks (e.g., GDPR). In cross-country and cross-institutional collaborations, a single DMP may be subject to multiple, and sometimes conflicting, policy environments. Making policy references a clear, structured part of the DMP enables teams to identify overlaps, gaps, or legal obligations early, supporting compliance and responsible data handling across borders.</p>

The complete, re-designed template in its preliminary stage can be consulted in the [Annex I: Updated HE DMP Template to serve as a pilot for FP10](#).

5.2. DMP-related Benchmarks for Semi-Automated Assessment

To support scalable and consistent DMP review that reflects the validated dimensions, we recommend implementing the identified benchmarks and metrics that are progressively becoming available in the evaluation service.

Key actions include:

- **Select the benchmarks and metrics available at the DMP evaluation service** to assess partly or in full the seven DMP evaluation dimensions: Content Completeness, RDM Coverage, Feasibility, Openness, FAIRness, DCS Compliance, and Policy Compliance.

- **Use structured data fields and PIDs in the templates** to enable machine-readable assessment and alignment with FAIR metrics and DMP Common Standard fields.
- **Develop APIs and scoring outputs compliant to the OSTrails Assessment Framework** to integrate with funder workflows, institutional review processes, and reporting tools.

Initial prototypes of this service have been tested within the [ARGOS platform](#) under the OSTrails Horizon Europe pilot, confirming the feasibility of semi-automated checks and their alignment with national funder expectations. **Table 11** shows an example benchmark to assess the FAIRness of the DMP itself as an independent resource type, along with an example API to call the DMP evaluation service's benchmarks.

Table 11. Ongoing work on the DMP Evaluation Service

DMP-RELATED BENCHMARK FOR FAIR DMPs	Metrics				
	Field	Value	Tests		
	ID	fair.dmp	Test ID	Description	Input Output
	Title	FAIR DMP Output	T-DCSC	Checks that there is dmp_id	.json maDMP pass/fail
	Narrative	The DMP is shared in a repository with a license and PID.		Checks that there are "identifier" and "type"	.json maDMP pass/fail or weighted
	Dimension	FAIRness			
			Test ID	Checks that there is dmp_license	.json maDMP pass/fail
			T-DCSC	Checks that there are "license_ref" and "start_date"	.json maDMP pass/fail or weighted
			Test ID	Checks that there is dmp_host	.json maDMP pass/fail
			T-DCSC	Checks that there are "title" and "uri"	.json maDMP pass/fail or weighted
Benchmark API Example	<pre>[{ "benchmarkId": "string", "title": "string", "description": "string", "version": "string", "hasAssociatedMetric": ["string"], "algorithms": ["string"], "keyword": "string", "abbreviation": "string", "landingPage": "string", "theme": "string", "status": "string", "creator": ["string"] }]</pre>				

To complement and test this conceptual work, we present an example from the first implementation in ARGOS. **Figure 15** shows the result from calling the DMP evaluation service's [DCS compliance benchmark](#) in order to assess the machine actionability of the displayed DMP.

Figure 15. ARGOS adoption of the maDMP evaluation framework

5.3. Application of the OSTrails maDMP Profile

The OSTrails maDMP Application Profile provides the technical foundation for harmonised, machine-actionable planning across Europe.

Key actions include:

- **Further develop the OSTrails Application Profile** following community consultations with pilots that are working in different settings, eg thematic research infrastructures.
- **Support community adoption** by publishing clear documentation, mappings to funder templates, and real-world examples.
- **Maintain alignment with the RDA DMP Common Standard** while extending functionality through new entities for policy, methodology, roles, and identifiers.
- Enable cross-platform validation and FAIR compliance by embedding semantic hooks and **extending repository interoperability fields**.

Wider implementation of the profile ensures interoperability, policy compliance, and FAIRness across all phases of the research lifecycle, across Horizon Europe projects and national funders. This profile supports machine-actionable planning, evaluation, and monitoring based on the DMP Common Standard.

Below we present a maDMP export from ARGOS that incorporates in green colour the changes as presented in the requirements (see [3.3](#)).

Table 12. Part of preliminary OSTrails maDMP new JSON.

```

{ "dmp": {
  "dmp_status": "draft",
    "related_identifiers": [{
      "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.12345",
      "identifierType": "DOI",
      "relationType": "IsDocumentedBy",
    }],
    "policies": [{
      "title": "TUWien Open Science Policy",
      "description": "Describes institutional RDM
obligations",
      "policy_type": "institutional",
      "jurisdiction": "European Union",
      "related_identifiers": [{
        "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.9876",
        "identifierType": "DOI",
        "relationType": "Describes",
      }
    ]
  }],
  "dmp_license": {
    "license_ref":
"https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
    "start_date": "2024-03-01",
    "access_rights": "open",
  },
  "title": "Horizon Europe Pilot - Plan"
}

```

For the full preliminary JSON export of the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile, check the [Annex II](#).

6. Conclusions and Next Steps

This deliverable marks a key milestone in OpenAIRE's implementation of the **OSTrails Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) Framework** to improve how Data Management Plans (DMPs) are designed, evaluated, and reused across Horizon Europe. By integrating evidence from funders, research communities, and service providers, this first version of the Horizon Europe pilot Report demonstrates how actionable, standards-aligned, and interoperable DMP practices can be implemented at scale.

Three interconnected outcomes were achieved:

- **A revised Horizon Europe DMP template** that addresses known limitations in structure, usability, and stakeholder role clarity—introducing a two-layered design (declarations vs. implementation) to support both researchers and support staff.
- **A validated set of evaluation dimensions** that reflect shared priorities across funders and institutions—especially in areas such as content completeness, openness, FAIRness, and policy alignment—along with benchmarks that underpin the beta version of the OSTrails DMP evaluation service.
- **The first version of the OSTrails maDMP Application Profile**, extending the RDA DMP Common Standard with structured fields for roles, policy references, dataset methodology, repository trust, and licensing. The profile has been tested in ARGOS and will continue to guide technical alignment and service interoperability across national and institutional settings.

Together, these outputs offer a coherent foundation to improve planning, monitoring, and evaluation of research outputs in Horizon Europe. They promote structured, machine-actionable practices that are aligned with FAIR principles and support the digital transformation of science.

The next phase of work will focus on **broadening engagement, extending implementation**, and **refining the outputs** based on real-world feedback and final results stemming from the technical work performed in OSTrails:

- **Pilot Expansion and Validation:** The 24 OSTrails pilots spanning various scientific domains, countries, and infrastructures will test the revised DMP template, maDMP profile, and evaluation service in their technical environments. Results from these pilots will inform final refinements and national alignment efforts.
- **Further Stakeholder Involvement:** The next version of this work will include structured input from institutional actors such as **data stewards, librarians, IT and legal departments, ethics committees, and DPOs**. Their operational knowledge is critical for ensuring that templates, evaluations, and workflows are feasible and inclusive.
- **Direct Outreach to Horizon Europe Projects:** Structured engagement with Horizon Europe project investigators will be carried out to better understand how DMPs are authored, reviewed, and updated in practice. This includes exploring actual workflows, identifying common blockers, and promoting adoption of the revised tools and services. [6]
- **Integration into OpenAIRE and EOSC services:** The outputs of this work will continue to be embedded into OpenAIRE's Graph, ARGOS platform and the FAIR Validator, ensuring direct alignment with EC project reporting workflows and the broader EOSC interoperability ecosystem.
- **Contribution to FP10 and Policy Uptake:** As the European Commission prepares the next Framework Programme (FP10), the results of this work will be positioned as

a concrete, tested approach for revising DMP requirements, strengthening Open Science monitoring, and enabling harmonised policy implementation across Member States.

This is the beginning of a broader shift: from treating DMPs as static compliance documents to making them dynamic, FAIR-aligned research tools that support transparency, reuse, and evaluation across the full research lifecycle.

Annex I: Updated HE DMP Template to serve as a pilot for FP10

SUGGESTED DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TEMPLATE FOR USE in FP 10

This template is proposed in the context of the EU funded OSTrails Project WP 4, Task 4.2. (Horizon Europe Pilot). Please see supplementary documentation for further information.

0. COVER PAGE

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:
 Project Manager / Data Manager AND / OR Researcher in charge (e.g. Principal Investigator (PI))

PROJECT	
Project number:	[project number]
Project acronym:	[acronym]
Project name:	[project title]
Project description:	[project summary]
Project implementation period:	[start/end date]
Deliverable:	[Number and Name]
Dissemination Level:	[PU / CO / EU-RES] – justify if not PU
ROLES & RESPONSIBILITIES	
MAIN CONTACT	
Main contact for DMP:	[Name]
Affiliation:	[Organisation]
ORCID:	[0000-000X-XXXX-XXXX]
Email:	[email address]
CONTRIBUTORS	
Contributors	[Name]
Affiliations	[Organisations]
Contributors' roles	e.g. data stewards, repository manager / IT experts, legal officers, data protection officers, ethics committees etc.

ORCID(s)	[0000-000X-XXXX-XXXX]
Emails	[email addresses]
ABOUT THE DMP	
Title:	[DMP Name]
Description:	[...]
PID:	[10.XXXX/xxxxx]
License:	[CC-BY]
Date of creation:	[dd/mm/yyyy]
Date of last modification:	[dd/mm/yyyy]
DMP Version:	[number of DMP version]
Summary of key changes in new version:	[logs]

1. PROJECT'S DMP STRATEGY & EXPECTED OUTPUTS

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:

All Relevant Consortium Partners AND their institutional research support structures, if available.

(e.g. Project Manager AND / OR Researcher in charge / Data Manager / Legal Staff / Data Protection Officers etc)

1.1 Overview

Provide a brief summary of your overall consortium strategy for managing the data created and / or used in the project.

- *Explain the purpose of data activities and link to project objectives and expected outputs.*
- *Describe anticipated users beyond the project and the usability of data post-project (utility).*

1.2 Dataset Summary - Inventory

Complete the following dataset table to describe collected, generated and / or reused datasets, and identify the data manager or person responsible for its upkeep.

Dataset ID	Title	Repository	Reuse/Generated	Origin/provenance of new data	Data Types	Personal Data	Sensitive Data	Metadata standards	Methodology	Controlled Vocabularies	Tools used for RDM	Quality assurance processes	Access Level	License	Format	PID System	Size	Retention Period	Qualified References	Data Manager
[doi: 10.XXX X/xxxxx]	[Dataset title]	[Zenodo]	[Reuse]	[Describe how the new data was originated and its provenance]	[Image]	[Yes/No]	[Yes/No]	[URL of metadata]	[Description of the methodology used to collect, process and/or analyse the data]	[Ontology X]	[Tools used to access, analyse, store the data]	[Description of quality checks applied]	[Open, restricted, embargoed, closed]	[CC-BY]	[png]	[DOI]	[1234]	[2025-07-31]	[Related datasets, publications or software with persistent identifiers]	[Name - 0000-000X-XXXX-XXXX]

Every dataset entry of the inventory should be accompanied by a thorough description of expected and / or applied RDM practices

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:
 Data Steward, Librarian or equivalent, Researchers, Repository Manager, Legal Staff

1.2.1 Reuse of Existing Data

- Indicate if you assessed existing data before generating new data.
- If reuse was not possible, explain why (e.g., no suitable data, legal restrictions, quality issues).

1.2.2 Data Sharing, Embargoes & Access

- Specify when and how the dataset will be made openly available.
- If not immediately open, explain any embargo period (reason and duration).
- Provide the repository name, type (institutional, domain-specific, general-purpose), and whether it is trusted (e.g., CoreTrustSeal certified).
- Clarify the access conditions (open, restricted, under request, authentication).

1.2.3 Documentation & Metadata

- Describe what documentation will support reuse (e.g., README, codebook, protocols).
- Indicate which metadata standard(s) you will use (e.g., Dublin Core, DataCite, schema.org).
- Confirm whether metadata will be:
 - Discoverable/indexed (e.g., in OpenAIRE, EOSC)
 - Harvestable via standard protocols (e.g., OAI-PMH)
 - Released under CC0 or an open license
- List the main metadata fields that support discovery (title, abstract, keywords, creators, related outputs).
- If you use custom vocabularies or terms, state whether and how you will map them to standard vocabularies (e.g., SKOS, RDF).

1.2.4 Interoperability & Standards

- Provide references to relevant standards, schemas, or controlled vocabularies used (especially for metadata, formats, identifiers).
- Indicate if metadata validation will be applied, and which tools or schema are used (e.g., validation against repository requirements or a maDMP profile).

1.2.5 Preservation & Longevity

- State how long the data and metadata will be preserved (minimum 5–10 years, or longer as per discipline/institution/funder).
- Explain who is responsible (e.g., data steward, institution, repository) and what infrastructure ensures this.
- Confirm that both data and metadata will remain accessible and usable (e.g., by using open formats, structured metadata, repository commitments).

1.2.6 Versioning

- Explain how versions will be managed and differences tracked.
- Indicate whether each version will have a separate PID (e.g., DOI).
- Briefly describe your versioning strategy (e.g., semantic versioning, changelog).

1.2.7 Unused Data

- State whether data not included in publications will also be archived.
- Describe how and where this data will be stored (with or separate from published data).

1.3 Data Security

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:

Data Protection Officer / IT Staff

- How will the data be securely stored and backed up during the project? Specify whether institutional infrastructure will be used (e.g., university servers, secure cloud services) and detail any access controls or monitoring measures in place.
- How will data be securely stored and archived after the project?
- What procedures will be used to delete data securely, especially for personal / sensitive datasets?

2. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUT

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:

Project Manager / Researcher

- *Digital Output: What (if any) software, workflows, models, or protocols will be created or re-used? Include licensing, versioning, and repository plans.*
- *Physical Output: What (if any) samples, reagents and materials will be created or re-used?*

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:

Project Manager / Data Steward or equivalent, Repository Manager

- *What are the estimated costs associated with data storage, documentation, curation, and making data FAIR throughout the project duration? Indicate whether these are covered in the project budget and how they will be managed.*
- *What are the expected costs for long-term data preservation after the project ends (e.g., repository fees, cold storage, curation services). Indicate how these costs will be covered, who is responsible, and for how long the data will be retained. How will these be covered?*
- *Who is responsible for long-term data preservation?*

4. ETHICS

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:

Legal Experts / Staff responsible for ethics, Researcher – avoid duplication with ethics processes.

- *Will a Data Access Committee be established?*
- *Will informed consent cover data sharing and long-term preservation?*
- *What ethical or legal issues could impact data sharing?*
- *Link to the ethics section of the DoA, if applicable.*

5. NATIONAL / SECTORAL POLICIES AND REQUIREMENTS

Stakeholder Responsible for filling in this section:

Project Manager / Data Steward or equivalent

- *Will other national, disciplinary or funder-specific RDM policies and / or practices be followed? Describe your datasets according to your institutional research data management policies / DMP templates (where applicable).*

Annex II: Full example of preliminary OSTrails maDMP Application Profile

Below we present the JSON export of the ARGOS maDMP that includes the new entities and properties as defined in Section 5. These are presented in green fonts.

```
{
  "dmp": {
    "contact": {
      "contact_id": {
        "identifier": "754783ca-309e-4f3f-8f38-4d80008a04dd",
        "type": "other"
      },
      "mbox": "test.argos01@gmail.com",
      "name": "ARGOS 1",
      "affiliation": [{
        "name": "Athena Research Center",
        "affiliation_id": {
          "type": "ror",
          "identifier": "https://ror.org/XXXXX"
        }
      ]
    },
    "contributor": [
      {
        "contributor_id": {
          "identifier": "e8371ac6-4508-4c30-a453-3550e75cd4b9",
          "type": "other"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```

"mbox": "test.argos01@gmail.com",
"name": "ARGOS 1",
"role": [
  "Owner",
  "Data Steward"
],
"affiliation": [{
  "name": "Athena Research Center",
  "affiliation_id": {
    "type": "ror",
    "identifier": "https://ror.org/XXXXXX"
  }
}]
},
],
"cost": [
  {
    "description": "Cost Description",
    "title": "Title of cost",
    "value": 123456.0
  }
],
"created": "2025-07-15T15:23:38.492960Z",
"dataset": [
  {
    "dataset_id": {
      "identifier": "cf00fe2d-1608-4e84-ac01-
f410da83afee",
      "type": "other"
    },
    "dataset_status": "completed",
    "target_audience": ["researchers",
"policy_makers"],
    "methodology": {

```

```

        "methodology_id": {
            "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.67890",
            "type": "doi"
        },
        "description": "Survey with sampling design"
    },
    "language": "eng",
    "personal_data": "unknown",
    "sensitive_data": "unknown",
    "title": "Administration",
    "type": "DMP Dataset"
},
{
    "dataset_id": {
        "identifier": "4e7da8e1-8890-4b3e-9c00-
c7e923c71d1f",
        "type": "other"
    },
    "dataset_status": "draft",
    "target_audience": ["researchers",
"policy_makers"],
    "methodology": {
        "methodology_id": {
            "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.67890",
            "type": "doi"
        },
        "description": "Data from RadarXX"
    },
    "language": "eng",
    "personal_data": "unknown",
    "sensitive_data": "unknown",
    "title": "Horizon Europe test",
    "type": "DMP Dataset"
}

```

```

    },
    {
      "data_quality_assurance": [
        "n/a"
      ],
      "dataset_id": {
        "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.14795222",
        "type": "other"
      },
      "dataset_status": "completed",
      "target_audience": ["researchers",
"policy_makers"],
      "methodology": {
        "methodology_id": {
          "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.67890",
          "type": "doi"
        },
        "description": "Archaeological Dataset"
      },
      "description": "<p>This deliverable defines an
evaluation framework for machine-actionable Data Management
Plans (maDMPs), aiming to ensure alignment with FAIR principles and support
automated, interoperable assessments. By leveraging existing standards and
linking maDMPs to Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) through persistent
identifiers (PIDs), it identifies gaps, proposes improvements, and
outlines the next steps for future development.</p>",
      "distribution": [
        {
          "access_url":
"https://zenodo.org/records/14795222",
          "available_until": "2025-07-31",
          "byte_size": 134,
          "data_access": "open",
          "description": "<p>This deliverable
defines an evaluation framework for machine-actionable Data Management

```

Plans (maDMPs), aiming to ensure alignment with FAIR principles and support automated, interoperable assessments. By leveraging existing standards and linking maDMPs to Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) through persistent identifiers (PIDs), it identifies gaps, proposes improvements, and outlines the next steps for future development.

```

        "download_url":
"https://zenodo.org/records/14795222",
        "format": [
            "D3.1_DMP_Evaluation_Rubric_and_
Service_Specifications.pdf"
        ],
        "title": "D3.1 DMP Evaluation Rubric
and Service Specifications"
        "host": {
            "availability": "More than 99%
uptime yearly",
            "backup_frequency": "Hourly",
            "backup_type": "Incremental
backup",
            "certified_with": "iso16363",
            "description": "Repository
hosted by Zenodo",
            "geo_location": "CH",
            "pid_system": [
                "doi"
            ],
            "storage_type": "All files
uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes
disk cluster.",
            "title": "Zenodo",
            "url": "https://zenodo.org"
        }
        "license": [
            {
                "license_ref": "cc-by-4.0",
                "start_date": "2025-01-31"
            }
        ]
    ]
}

```

```

    }
  ],
  "restriction_explanation": " Contains
personal data under GDPR"
}
],
"issued": "2025-01-31",
"keyword": [
  "DMP",
  "Evaluation"
],
"language": "eng",
"metadata": [
  {
    "description": "DataCite Metadata
Schema",
    "language": "eng"
  }
],
"personal_data": "no",
"preservation_statement": "Deposited",
"security_and_privacy": [
  {
    "description": "Description",
    "title": "Measure"
  }
],
"sensitive_data": "no",
"technical_resource": [
  {
    "description": "Description of mapping
process",
    "name": "Mapping"
  }
]

```

```

    }
  ],
  "title": "D3.1 DMP Evaluation Rubric and Service
Specifications",
  "type": "Deliverable"
}
],
"description": "Description of the Plan",
"dmp_id": {
  "identifier": "6b214856-6c92-4864-b5d0-dd16193a238d",
  "type": "other"
},
"ethical_issues_description": "Ethical Issues",
"ethical_issues_exist": "unknown",
"language": "eng",
"modified": "2025-07-15T15:27:40.001134Z",
"project": [
  {
    "funding": [
      {
        "funder_id": {
          "identifier":
"ec_____::EC||European Commission||EC",
          "type": "fundref"
        },
        "funding_status": "applied",
        "grant_id": {
          "identifier":
"corda_____he::101130187",
          "type": "other"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

```

    }
  ],
  "dmp_status": "draft",
  "related_identifiers": [{
    "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.12345",
    "identifierType": "DOI",
    "relationType": "IsDocumentedBy",
  }],
  "policies": [{
    "title": "TUWien Open Science Policy",
    "description": "Describes institutional RDM
obligations",
    "policy_type": "institutional",
    "jurisdiction": "European Union",
    "related_identifiers": [{
      "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.9876",
      "identifierType": "DOI",
      "relationType": "Describes",
    }
  ]
}],
  "dmp_license": {
    "license_ref":
"https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
    "start_date": "2024-03-01",
    "access_rights": "open",
  },
  "title": "Horizon Europe Pilot - Plan"
}
}

```


References

- [1] Papadopoulou, E., Kontopidi, M., Miksa, T., & Romero, A. (2025). D3.1 DMP Evaluation Rubric and Service Specifications. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795222>
- [2] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- [3] Papadopoulou, E., Bardi, A., Kakaletiris, G. et al. Data management plans as linked open data: exploiting ARGOS FAIR and machine actionable outputs in the OpenAIRE research graph. *J Biomed Semant* 14, 17 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-023-00297-5>
- [4] Miksa, T., Wilkinson, M., Manghi, P., & Suchánek, M. (2025). D1.4 OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795000>
- [5] Miksa, T., Suchánek, M., Slifka, J., Knaisl, V., Ekaputra, F.J., Kovacevic, F., Ningtyas, A.M., El-Ebshihy, A. and Pergl, R. (2023) 'Towards a Toolbox for Automated Assessment of Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans', *Data Science Journal*, 22(1), p. 28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2023-028>.
- [6] Spichtinger D. Data Management Plans in Horizon 2020: what beneficiaries think and what we can learn from their experience [version 2; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. *Open Res Europe* 2022, 1:42 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.13342.2>)